

seedlings/pot. Sixteen pots, 2/variety, were caged with viruliferous BPH of each biotype for 24 h at 5 insects/seedling. One month after inoculation, percentage of infected seedlings was recorded. Mawee, Hathili, Murungakayan, and IR50

had less RSV infection regardless of biotype. IR22 and TN1 had higher percent infection for the three biotypes (see table). For all varieties tested, reaction to RSV infection with the three BPH biotypes was similar to their reaction to the

biotypes. Results indicate that varietal reaction to RSV varies with reaction to BPH biotype vector; therefore a degree of correlation exists between BPH and RSV resistance. □

Use of a lignin-specific dye to demonstrate phloem feeding by brown planthopper (BPH)

Z. R. Khan, postdoctoral fellow, Entomology Department, IRRI; and R. C. Saxena, principal research scientist, International Centre of Insect Physiology and Ecology, Nairobi, Kenya, and associate entomologist, IRRI

Microtomy of plant tissue on which the BPH has fed, qualitative and quantitative biochemical analyses of excreta, and its indicator chemical reactions have been relied upon to demonstrate phloem feeding by BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) on the rice plant. We confirmed phloem feeding by BPH on susceptible and resistant rice varieties by using safranin, a lignin-specific dye that is selectively translocated in xylem vessels and would indicate xylem feeding if the excreta were red.

Roots of 10-d-old seedlings of BPH biotype 1-susceptible TN1, and resistant ASD7 were immersed in a 0.2% aqueous solution of safranin 0 for about 6 h. After washing off the excess dye, groups of 2 or 3 treated seedlings were transferred to water-filled, small glass beakers or plastic containers in mylar cages. Ten

Filter paper discs on which honeydew of BPH biotype 1 was collected when the insect fed on susceptible TN1 and resistant ASD7 rice varieties. Bluish amino acid spots on ninhydrin-treated filter paper discs (c, d) indicate more phloem feeding on TN1, while the absence of red spots on filter paper discs (a, b) indicates lack of xylem feeding on both susceptible and resistant varieties.

newly emerged BPH biotype 1 females were then allowed to feed for 24 h on the seedlings, at the base of each of which was placed a 9-cm-diameter filter paper disc. A set of untreated seedlings were infested similarly as a control. The honeydew excreted by the hoppers dropped on the filter paper disc and was readily absorbed.

The BPH is primarily a phloem feeder because no red honeydew spots were detected on filter paper discs (Fig. 1a,b) Although the amount of BPH honeydew excreted was less on resistant ASD7 than on susceptible TN1 plants, the appearance of bluish amino acid spots indicated phloem feeding when filter paper discs from control seedlings were treated with 0.1% ninhydrin acetone solution (Fig. 1c,d). □

The BPH is primarily a phloem feeder

Electronically recorded waveforms associated with feeding behavior of green leafhopper (GLH)

Z. R. Khan, postdoctoral fellow, Entomology Department, IRRI; and R. C. Saxena, principal research scientist, International Centre of Insect Physiology and Ecology, Kenya, and associate entomologist, IRRI

We used an electronic feeding recorder to monitor GLH *Nephotettix virescens* feeding on GLH-susceptible and resistant plants.

1. Schematic diagram of circuit and equipment for recording GLH feeding on rice, IRRI.

